
Pest management and control DISEASES

Collateral hosts of *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn causing sheath blight of rice

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Sheath blight (ShB) caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* has assumed endemic proportions in most rice growing areas in Kerala. We recorded *R. solani* incidence on plants grown in rice fallows and on common lowland weeds at several sites.

Plant parts showing *R. solani* symptoms were cut into small pieces, surface sterilized in 0.1% mercuric chloride, washed in 3 changes of sterile water, and transferred to sterile petri dishes containing potato dextrose agar (PDA). The *R. solani* isolates obtained were purified

using the hyphal tip method and maintained on PDA slants. Pathogenicity of the isolates was established by artificial inoculation on their respective host plants. The following plants were found to be collateral hosts of *R. solani*: *Sesamum indicum* L., *Arachis hypogaea* L., *Sesbania aculeata* Pers., wild colocasia, *Cyperus iria* L., *Fimbristylis miliacea* Vahl, *Apluda aristata* L., and *Monochoria vaginalis* Burm. F. Presl.

R. solani produced severe collar rot symptoms on *Sesamum* and caused severely infected plants to wilt and die. The fungus caused severe leaf and stem blight on groundnut *A. hypogaea*. Badly infected leaves were shed prematurely. On *S. aculeata*, the fungus produced severe collar rot symptoms at all plant growth stages.

Infected wild colocasia plants growing

in and around rice fields developed typical ShB symptoms on the petiole. The fungus caused leaf blight on *C. iria* and *F. miliaceae*. Dark-colored lesions were observed on the leaf sheath and leaves of *A. aristata*. The fungus caused typical ShB symptoms on the petioles of *M. vaginalis*. Cross-inoculation studies on rice plants showed that all the eight *R. solani* isolates listed, except that from *S. indicum*, produced typical ShB symptoms.

A. aristata and *M. vaginalis* are new weed hosts of *R. solani* in India. This is the first record of this fungus causing collar rot symptoms on *S. aculeata*. On groundnut in India, *R. solani* has not yet been recorded to cause leaf and stem blight under natural conditions.

Eliminating collateral weed hosts can help reduce the inoculum potential of the ShB pathogen. □

Morphology and serological relationship of penyakit merah virus in Malaysia and rice tungro virus in the Philippines

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Penyakit merah (red disease) (PMV) of rice plants in Malaysia and rice tungro (RTV) in the Philippines have several common properties, including symptoms, varietal reactions and transmission by the vector green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens*.

When we examined leaf dip preparations of PMV using 2% phosphotungstic acid on carbon-coated grids under an electron microscope, two morphologically distinct viral particles were detected. One was isometric and about 31-37 nm in diameter. The other was bacilliform and about 35 nm in diameter, with length varying from 148 to 175 nm. There usual-

ly were more isometric particles. The particles are similar to those associated with RTV in the Philippines, penyakit hebang in Indonesia, and yellow-orange leaf in Thailand.

The serological relationship between PMV and RTV was examined using latex

flocculation test. Positive reactions were detected when leaf extracts of PMV-infected rice plants were tested with latex sensitized with rice tungro bacilliform virus and/or rice tungro spherical virus, indicating that PMV and RTV are also caused by the two viruses. □

Sheath blight occurrence in rice nurseries

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Sheath blight (ShB) has damaged rice since 1979 in kharif and rabi seasons in West and East Godavari Districts. It reached epidemic levels in 1981 kharif and 1982 rabi, when it affected all varieties grown and significantly reduced yield. In early ShB infections, only adult plants at panicle initiation stage were affected. Since 1981 kharif wet nurseries have been affected at the research farm and in some farmers fields.

In 1981 and 1982 MTU8002 (Gouthami), MTU8089 (Vashista), MTU7029

(Swarna), MTU4569 (Sowbhagya), MTU-4407 (Vijaya Mahsuri), IR42, and IR36 and prerelease cultures MTU5 182, MTU-7633, IET6314, and IET7574 were severely affected in the nursery. In 1982-83 rabi no nursery infection was observed.

Most seedlings in the nursery had infected lower leaves but some had sheath and leaf infection. Seedling infection followed a normal pattern. Severe infection caused stunting. *Leersia hexandra* growing as a weed in the infected nursery also had typical ShB symptoms.

We studied the possible carry-over of nursery infection to adult plants by transplanting 30- to 35-day-old infected seedlings of 13 cultures. We recorded damage at regular intervals, starting 5 days after transplanting (DT). Healthy MTU7029

and MTU6024 (Laxmi) seedlings were planted to see if the inoculum was from the nursery or other sources.

No ShB infection was noticed until 52 DT, when most cultures showed symptoms (see table). Other cultures showed infection at 66 and 76 DT. Infection gradually increased for all cultures after 52 DT. At 100 DT some susceptible cultures showed almost 100% infection. The healthy MTU7029 and MTU6024 seedlings also developed infection, indicating that the inoculum might have been from a source other than the nursery. Late appearance of ShB symptoms (52 DT) also may indicate that carry-over of inoculum from nursery to adult plants is a remote possibility. □

Sheath blight infection carry-over from nursery to adult plants.

Culture	Hills observed (no.)	Sheath blight-infected hills (no.) at indicated time				
		52 DT	66 DT	76 DT	86 DT	100 DT
<i>Infected</i>						
MTU7029	152	24	67	131	140	150
MTU8002	152	1	24	59	86	88
MTU7633	152	15	41	79	96	142
MTU7030	152	4	25	58	100	147
MTU2281	152	3	18	60	96	145
MTU2292	152	1	1	14	38	74
MTU2066	80	1	8	25	36	36
MTU2194	152	0	2	5	25	81
MTU4865	114	0	0	5	26	76
MTU6117	76	0	0	10	26	50
MTU6613	152	8	43	93	125	152
IET6919	152	2	4	14	80	81
IET7235	152	2	4	8	25	51
<i>Healthy</i>						
MTU7029	152	25	69	120	130	152
MTU6024	152	20	60	115	128	150

Blast outbreak in Manipur

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Blast (Bl) caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* is the most important rice disease in the northeastern hill region of India. In Manipur, Bl severely damages crops when the weather is favorable. In 1982 kharif, Bl affected all the high yielding varieties (IR24, Pusa 33, and Punshi). Punshi was most damaged (Table 1).

Table 1. Neck blast in 5 varieties at Lamphalpat farm, Manipur.

Year	Neck blast (%)				
	Pusa 33	Punshi	IR24	Prasad	RCM2
1981	84.8	100	18.2	0.7	0
1982	36.9	98.9	15.0	0.7	11.9

We surveyed fields in 5 subdivisions (50 hills/field and 2 fields/subdivision, selected randomly). Percent neck Bl incidence was highest in Moidangpok and lowest in Sawombung (Table 2). □

Table 2. Neck blast incidence in Punshi during 1982 kharif in Central district, Manipur.

Subdivision	Village	Neck blast (%)
Thoubal	Thoubal	48.2
	Haothamamana	28.4
	Kakching	18.0
Bishenpur	Bishenpur	17.7
	Ningthoukhong	28.9
	Toubul	71.0
Imphal West I	Khumbong	85.0
	Moidangpok	100.0
Imphal West II	Lamphalpat	98.9
	Ningombam	84.0
	Wangoi	30.0
Imphal East	Sawombung	15.0
	Pungdongbam	18.0
Av		49.5

Occurrence of rice yellow dwarf disease in Patna (Bihar) India

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Rice yellow dwarf disease was discovered on ratooned Sita plants at the ARI Farm in Mithapur, Nov 1982. Infected plants were chlorotic with pronounced stunting and profuse tillering. Chlorotic leaves were a uniform pale yellow. Isolated patches of infected hills were observed in

the field. IET5852 rice plants and stubble in adjoining plots were disease free.

A disease transmission test of suspected diseased plants from the field was conducted with second-instar nymphs of *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant). Nymphs were allowed to feed on test samples for 48 h and were incubated 25 days before 48 h of inoculation feeding on 10-day-old healthy TN1 seedlings. Yellow dwarf symptoms developed in about a month, confirming the disease.

This report confirms the presence of yellow dwarf disease in Patna Bihar as was first reported in 1967. Further spread of the disease should be monitored, diseased plants should be removed from fields and destroyed, and resistant varieties should be planted. □

Purification and serological properties of rice grassy stunt virus 2

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Rice grassy stunt virus 2 (RGSV 2), a strain of rice grassy stunt virus (RGSV 1), was purified following the procedure for grassy stunt virus in Japan. The sap of infected plants was clarified with magnesium bentonite and carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄), treated with polyethylene glycol (PEG), and centrifuged in 10-45% sucrose density gradient. Electron microscopy of the purified fraction revealed numerous filamentous particles of various